

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SRIKUMAR****FIRST NAME: RUPASREE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 Pro)

WRITING WITH RIGHT STYLING

1) INTRODUCTION

The very first period in the very first course as part of the DIPH program in Euclid University aims at familiarizing students with the standards of writing, such as styling and referencing, that is followed in the EUCLID ecosystem. What seemed like a simple topic at the beginning, turned out to be an extensive subject, described by a comprehensive combination of text and video course pack that has been meticulously put together from varying sources, keeping in mind a wide range of target students. As is expected of a student, I write this response paper, not just *on* the topics discussed in the 83-page long course pack intended for this period, but also *following* them [emphasis added (EUCLID 2015, 70)].

2) BASIC DOS AND DON'TS

While the course pack discourages the usage of contractions like can't, don't (EUCLID 2015, 39), the above heading should be an acceptable exception owing to its common usage to denote the set of rules or customs that any activity or task is expected to meet. I aim to discuss some basic dos and don'ts in the context of academic writing, as promoted by EUCLID to its students, in the sub-sections below.

a) DOS

For an effective essay, one should start early, research extensively, plan adequately, organize the topics efficiently, write clearly, and read and reread thoroughly before

converting the first draft to the final copy for timely submission (EUCLID 2015, 2 to 5). Throughout the course of writing, giving rightful credits to the sources of information presented in the content with proper referencing is crucial. This process of giving credit is called citation, that as per *Turabian* style, can broadly be applied either as in-text (also called parenthetical) or as footnote, both of which should provide the reader with the information on the author and the page number(s) in the publication and is generally recommended to be supplemented with a complete list of works cited ('bibliography' or 'references') at the end of the essay (EUCLID 2015, 12 – 17).

As followed in this paper, EUCLID's response papers are mandated to use the former method of in-text referencing using *Turabian* style. Additionally, the information that is cited, can be presented either as a quotation or as a paraphrase, the difference between which lies in whether the writer uses the exact same words of the author of the source or delivers the underlying point of the author of the source in his/her own words, respectively. It is imperative to choose the right style of quoting; to use quotation *marks* ("") for short quotations and to use quotation *styling* (a feature of MS Word styles) for long quotations (EUCLID 2015, 18-21). Paraphrasing, on the other hand, should display a right balance between the choice of words and style that do not mimic the original writing but puts forth the information precisely (EUCLID 2015, 23-24). While structuring the essay, ensuring logical flow of information, and using what is called the signal phrases in the course pack, enhance the academic image of the essay and will help give the reader a holistic view of the topic (EUCLID 2015, 39-40).

Deciding on and being consistent in the variant of English, between American vs. British, is another important, but rarely highlighted, requirement. While the pdf course pack discusses the nuances between these variants (EUCLID 2015, 54-58), video (EUCLID 2019) explains how students can effectively use an MS Word proofing language feature to achieve the consistency. Incidentally, the pdf course pack fails to meet this consistency, by mentioning 'offense' on page 12 and 'offence' on page 5, that, however, can be reasoned out and ignored owing to its nature of being a compilation of different materials. Lastly, the course pack also broadly lays out and discusses some general rules of thumb and reminders on punctuations, grammar and vocabulary (EUCLID 2015, 43-51), that, I felt, is highly needed in today's world with growing use of texting/shortened languages, to revamp our basic English knowledge.

b) DON'Ts

As may be obvious, negligence of any of the points listed under the DOs is a clear DON'T. Of these, failing to give credit to the author of the source of information presented in the writing, is certainly, and rightfully, the most serious (EUCLID 2015, 8-9). This practice, named plagiarism, is strictly forbid and can land the doer in serious consequences. The only exception, would be common knowledge that does not require citation. This, however, needs extensive research to understand whether something is a common knowledge, especially when someone is new to the subject area (EUCLID 2015, 30-31). Contractions like can't, don't and so forth, are also to be avoided to help the essay retain its academic flavor (EUCLID 2015, 39). Another don't is to not quote a content that has

error, factual or grammatical, and resort to paraphrasing with the error removed (EUCLID 2015, 70).

c) Style guide

A documentation of all the styles and practices that are essential to be used or strictly not used, to warrant consistency across publications or even across different sections within a single writing, is called a style guide (EUCLID 2015, 52). Even though style guides are more associated with technical writing, than creative writing, this section in the course pack clearly describes why a style guide is essential for writers of both categories, with the difference only lying in the number of elements, such as manuscript length, font style and size, use of symbols and abbreviations, and so on., that may be relevant for them (EUCLID 2015, 53).

3) OTHER INSIGHTS

I found the section on sample correction to papers to be a great way to inform the students of what to expect when their RPs are reviewed (EUCLID 2015, 60-65). What particularly was interesting here is that the corrections ranged from as simple as adding a comma, suggestions of alternate words to communicate the meaning better, to commenting on whether the inference/conclusion is correct and consistent when read in the light of the introduction.

4) THE 'CMS' CHEAT SHEET

The 12-page-long CMS (Chicago Manual of Style) crib sheet explains, in an easy-to-understand style, when and where to abbreviate, capitalize, hyphenate, italicize, quote, as well as where to spell out numbers vs. use numerals, and how to effectively include and format lists, footnotes, endnotes, tables and headings. Personally being a fan of succinct-writing, as against text-heavy paragraphs, I thoroughly enjoyed reading the section on 'Headings & Lists', especially the usage of seriation/bullets, and 'Tables', as well as going through an actual table on Latin abbreviations, not just for detailing my favorite formatting style but also for adopting them and making my reading relatively easier (EUCLID 2015, 73-83). This sheet is sure to be included in my list of go-to resources while writing academic articles/papers. I also realized that I had a misconception that right justification is a must for formal documents, getting a clarity that the priority is the ease of reading, and a right justification that creates large spaces between words and thereby, making it difficult to read, is better avoided (EUCLID 2015, 72).

5) CONCLUSION

This course pack reinstated the importance of and guidelines to achieving both a good and a neat academic writing, while also setting up a strong base for the detailed knowledge that is to follow in this course. Having grown up in a majorly British English following country and moving on to work with Americans, my English had naturally picked up both tinges. Studying this material helped me recognize this and identify the predominant variant, the American, that I have chosen to adopt and be consistent in, in my papers going forward.

REFERENCES

Euclid University, 2015. *ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from: <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B/ACA-401%20Coursepack.pdf>

Euclid University, 2019. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Retrieved from: <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.